

EXERGY-OPTIMUM ENVIRONMENTAL DESIGN AND CONTROL OF MORPHING AIR-TO-AIR HEAT RECOVERY VENTILATION IN SUSTAINABLE BUILDINGS

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces an axially morphing heat recovery ventilation unit, which addresses the thermodynamic gaps in the current theory and practice due to the lack of recognition of the Second Law of thermodynamics, and the fixed design geometry and control parameters. Three major gaps are identified: 1-All standards, guides, and design practices and controls are based only on the First Law of Thermodynamics. 2-Exergy of fan power consisting of electric power and the exergy of thermal power obtained by the heat recovery process are different and additional carbon dioxide emission responsibility occurs in proportion to the difference. This recognition needs the second law. 3-The thermal effectiveness changes with instantaneous air-change demand and operating conditions, like the temperature of the outdoor air. But the design geometry and operating regime is constant except variable fan speed, if included in the design. To avoid these gaps a novel, axially morphing heat recovering exchanger has been modeled and analyzed using both the First and the Second laws. The model consists of an axially expanding or retracting heat exchanging chamber such that the decarbonization effect of the recovery is maximized. Sample analyses show that such a design may benefit up to 150% increase of carbon-dioxide reduction potential when electric power from a grid-connected natural-gas power plant is supplied, compared with a conventional design with fixed geometry, based on the First Law only. The impact of the new findings on several standards and green building metrics are discussed, and correction factors are introduced.

Keywords: Morphing HRV, Exergy, Nearly avoidable CO₂, Green Building Metric, Coefficient of Performance

INTRODUCTION

With the global warming due to CO₂ emissions in the built environment, the need for sustainable buildings and utilization and recovery of waste heat sources are becoming crucial. Every thousand Gton of CO₂ released to the atmosphere causes an increase in the global average temperature by 0.45°C [1]. An average of 37 Gton of CO₂ gas is released into the atmosphere every year because of energy use alone [2, 3]. The total emissions including other emission sources is 60 Gton/year. Buildings are responsible for 15.3 Gton alone. Despite such a high emission rate from the buildings, green building metrics are limited by the First Law of Thermodynamics, whereas nearly avoidable emissions, ΔCO_2 may be as high as seven times the direct emissions measured or predicted by the First Law in a building [4, 5]. Consequently, a net zero building according to energy efficiency calculations (First Law) may be responsible for ΔCO_2 due to exergy mismatches between energy supply and building loads satisfied by exergy-inefficient systems. Air-to-air heat recovery systems for ventilation of buildings (HRV) is one of them with three major literature gaps. These primary gaps are given below.

- 1- Heat recovery models and standards are based only on the First Law.
- 2- Fan power exergy and the exergy of the thermal power recovered are different.
- 3- The use of HRV units is based on fixed design and testing conditions.

In fact, operating conditions, and demand loads (fresh air requirement, etc.) are instantly changing

variables, which variably affect CO₂ emission responsibilities.

To avoid further global warming effect from HRV or ERV systems, the performance ratings and controls must prioritize the control of emission responsibilities. Yet, current standards and guidebooks do not relate First Law efficiency and effectiveness directly to emissions. For example, in AHRI Standard 1061-SI-2018, mass and ‘energy’ inequalities are the only testing and rating factors. In this respect, the sensible energy inequality is a function of $mC_p\Delta T$, and the resulting CO₂ emissions are not described, whereas if an exergy imbalance would be considered, then the exergy imbalance, namely $mC_p\Delta T(1-T_0/T_1)$, according to the ideal Carnot Cycle would result in ΔCO_2 , according to the following expression [6]:

$$\Delta\text{CO}_2 = k \times \text{Exergy Imbalance (Destruction)} = k \times \varepsilon_{des} \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, the proportionality factor, k is either 1.1 or 2.1, depending upon where the major exergy destruction due to exergy imbalance takes place. It is 1.1 if it takes place downstream of the useful application, like a solar PV panel (destroys thermal exergy after generating electric power), and 2.1 if the useful application like HRV takes place after the utilization of power (electrical input to the fans).

Figure 1 shows a simple diagram about air-to air heat recovery in ventilation (HRV), without recirculation of the exhaust air, as described in ASHRAE Handbook S 26 an S 41.4 [7-a, 7-b]. According to the First Law of Thermodynamics, the coefficient of performance, COP is a simple ratio of the amount of thermal power recovered (heat or cold), Q to the total fan power demand term, $(P_e + P_s)$, which includes the fan and motor efficiencies according to the First Law. Such an analysis does not recognize the relation between exergy destructions and ΔCO_2 .

$$COP = \frac{Q}{(P_e + P_s)} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Sensible Heat Exchanger, HRV [7, 8].

Figure 2. The Exergy Flow Diagram of HRV. Exergy Destruction between T_0 and T_r is Ignored.

Furthermore, ASHRAE HB F21 Duct Design [9], discussing the total fan power, does not recognize the exergy differences between fan power and thermal power supplied or circulated. To avoid the gap in the

literature, including several standards, they must be subjected to the Second Law [10]. In this respect, Figure 1 should be accompanied by Figure 2, which shows the exergy imbalance between the high unit exergy of fan power demand ($0.95 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{h}_{\text{ex}}/\text{kW}\cdot\text{h}_{\text{en}}$) and the thermal exergy recovered by the HRV. According to Standard ASHRAE 90.1 [11], ERV unit is mandatory when a building's outdoor fresh air supply is greater than $8500 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, less than 30% air recirculation is present, and the total effectiveness must be higher than 50%. All these constraints and limitations described in the Standard are simply based on the First Law. i.e. temperature differences are a variable in (T_1-T_2) type of expressions, but their ratios are not factored in according to the Second Law in the form of an ideal Carnot Cycle factor $(1-T_1/T_2)$, which presents the useful work potential of the heat transfer. For example, if T_1 is 273 K and T_2 is 290 K, ΔT is 17 K with the Carnot factor of $(1-273\text{K}/290\text{K})=0.0586$. However, the same ΔT may hold for different T_1 and T_2 values, which render quite different Carnot Factors, like if T_1 is 283 K and T_2 310 K, ΔT is still 17 K, but the Carnot factor is 0.0871, a difference of about 50%. This comparison means that at the absence of temperature levels in determining the actual environmental usefulness of HRV or similar units Standard 90.1, will either overestimate or underestimate the CO_2 emission mitigation or responsibility. In addition, ASHRAE Standard 90.1 Tables 6.5.6.1-1, and 6.5.3.1 prescribes fan power limitations, ($1.896 \text{ kW}/\text{m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$), for flow rates less than $9.44 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ for the US climate zone of 7, B. For a comprehensive environmental analysis this simplistic approach should recognize several other parameters like where the electric power comes from to the fans, temperature levels of heat exchange, and whether the HRV or ERV units cooperate with heat pumps [12].

Example

If Q is 1 kW, and (P_e+P_s) is 0.1 kW in Figure 1, according to the First Law models in these Standards and others, the COP of HRV is 10. Then if the existing literature and standards are extended for CO_2 emissions by comparing the same amount of heat recovery supplied by an onsite natural gas-condensing boiler (Reference), with an average First Law-efficiency, $i_f(0.90)$, an apparent emission savings is calculated. In Equation 3, the Primary Energy Factor, PEF is 2.5 (EU Average). This model obviously ignores all ΔCO_2 terms and simply considers that HRV consumes electrical energy from a grid-connected power plant (pp), thus responsible from CO_{2-pp} amount of emissions, but replaces the emissions of the reference boiler. The net result is a modest CO_2 mitigation.

$$\text{CO}_2 = \text{CO}_{2-pp} - \text{CO}_{2-HRV} = 0.2 \times Q \times \left[\frac{PEF}{COP} - \frac{1}{\eta_{IB}} \right] = -0.172 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{h} \quad \{\text{First Law CO}_2 \text{ Mitigation}\} \quad (3)$$

If the Second Law and Equation 1 are considered to determine the ΔCO_2 responsibility, and according to the new model given in this paper, it is recognized that the unit thermal exergy recovered depends on T_o and T_1 [13, 14]. Therefore, the unit exergy mismatch must be considered to determine ΔCO_2 using the Rational Exergy Management Model, REMM [15, 16].

$$\Delta\text{CO}_{2-HRV} = 2.1 \times \left[0.95 \times (P_e + P_s) - Q \times \left(1 - \frac{T_o}{T_1} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

Carbon mitigation potential referenced to a boiler in heat recovery, including elimination of its exergy destruction (The second term in Equation 5):

$$CO_{2-boiler} = Q \times \left[\frac{0.2}{\eta_{IB}} + 2.1 \times \left\{ \frac{0.87}{\eta_{IB}} - \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_1} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (5)$$

$$\sum CO_2 = \Delta CO_{2-HRV} - CO_{2-boiler} \quad (6)$$

Whether the HRV unit described in this case is responsible from emissions or mitigates carbon depends on the sign of Equation 6. If $\sum CO_2$ is >0 then, this unit is responsible for emissions. If $\sum CO_2 < 0$, then the unit mitigates carbon. If the result is zero, then the unit is neutral. Therefore, certain constraints and definitions are in order. With the following additional temperature variables and if the unit CO_2 content of natural gas is $0.2 \text{ kg } CO_2/kW\text{-}h_{en}$:

$T_0 = 273 \text{ K}$, $T_2 = 278 \text{ K}$, Power plant stack temperature = 700 K , Reference temperature = 273 K .

$$\Delta CO_{2-HRV} = 2.1 \times \left[0.95 \times 0.1 - 1 \times \left(1 - \frac{273 \text{ K}}{278 \text{ K}} \right) \right] = 0.162 \text{ kg } CO_2/h$$

$$CO_{2-pp} + \Delta CO_{2-pp} = 0.2 \times 1 \times \left[\frac{2.5}{10} \right] \left\{ 1 + 1.1 \times (1 - 0.4) \times \left(1 - \frac{273 \text{ K}}{700 \text{ K}} \right) \right\} = 0.070 \text{ kg } CO_2/h$$

The total CO_2 emission responsibility of HRV is the sum of ΔCO_{2-HRV} , CO_{2-pp} , and ΔCO_{2-pp} , as prescribed by the Second Law = $0.232 \text{ kg } CO_2/h$. On the other hand, the HRV unit replaces a reference boiler on site. The first term is the direct emissions from the boiler and the second term is the exergy destruction of the boiler, both of which are avoided by using HRV.

$$CO_{2-boiler} = 1 \times \left[\frac{0.2}{0.90} + 2.1 \times \left\{ \frac{0.87}{0.90} - \left(1 - \frac{273 \text{ K}}{278 \text{ K}} \right) \right\} \right] = 2.21 \text{ kg } CO_2/h \quad \{\text{Reference is a boiler}\}$$

$$\sum CO_2 = (0.232 - 2.21) \text{ kg } CO_2/h = -1.98 \text{ kg } CO_2/h \quad \{\text{CO}_2 \text{ mitigated}\}$$

This CO_2 mitigation potential result is quite higher than what the First Law predicts in Equation 3 ($-0.172 \text{ kg } CO_2/h$), mainly because HRV unit avoids a large exergy destruction of the upstream of the boiler heating to provide Q . However, if the reference equipment is a solar flat-plate collector (FPC) for hot water production in the heating season (solar insolation is less, therefore the unit exergy of solar irradiation is taken $0.40 \text{ kW-h}_{ex}/\text{kW-h}_{en}$, as a given and the thermal efficiency is 0.6) compared, the potential mitigation difference is less (Compare to $-1.98 \text{ kg } CO_2/h$):

$$CO_{2-FPC} = 1 \times \left[2.1 \times \left\{ \frac{0.40}{0.6} - \left(1 - \frac{273 \text{ K}}{278 \text{ K}} \right) \right\} \right] = 1.36 \text{ kg } CO_2/h \quad \{\text{Reference is FPC}\}$$

Such a change in the CO_2 mitigation potential with the reference equipment shows that where the power comes from, which fuel is used, the season of operation: air preheating or pre-cooling mode of operation, temperatures involved and by which systems and equipment (references) are employed is very important.

$$\sum CO_2 = (0.232 - 1.36) \text{ kg } CO_2/h = -1.13 \text{ kg } CO_2/h \quad \{\text{CO}_2 \text{ mitigated}\}$$

Results also depend on the COP of the HRV. For example, if COP is four with $(P_e + P_i) = 0.25 \text{ kW}$:

$$\Delta CO_{2-HRV} = 2.1 \times \left[0.95 \times 0.25 - 1 \times \left(1 - \frac{273 \text{ K}}{278 \text{ K}} \right) \right] = 0.46 \text{ kg } CO_2/h$$

$$CO_{2-pp} + \Delta CO_{2-pp} = 0.2 \times 1 \times \left[\frac{2.5}{4} \right] \left\{ 1 + 1.1 \times \left(1 - \frac{273 \text{ K}}{650 \text{ K}} \right) \right\} = 0.205 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{h}$$

$$\sum CO_2 = (0.46 + 0.205 - 1.13) \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{h} = -0.46 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{h} \quad \{\text{Less CO}_2 \text{ mitigated}\}$$

This result shows that the geometrical design of HRV is also crucial which lets to think about a morphing HRV, which can respond to different operating conditions for maintaining a high COP all the time for minimum emission responsibility. A morphing HRV can also change the T_i supply temperature at an expense of fan power or vice versa. The new model shows that HRV is favorable when compared to a boiler or solar FPC. However, such a broad analysis also guides the designer to arrive at better solutions, like a natural gas driven micro-CHP system (μ CHP) [17], which generates both electric power and heat. In this case the HRV may not compete with a natural gas-driven μ CHP which typically has less than 0.5 kg CO_2/h ($Q=1$) responsibility, which may be derived from Equation 8, by the definition given in Equations 8 and 1.

$$\psi_R = 1 - \frac{\mathcal{E}_{des}}{\mathcal{E}_{sup}} \quad (7)$$

$$\sum CO_{2-\mu CHP} = 1.1 \times \varepsilon_{sup} \times Q \times (1 - \psi_R) + \frac{0.2}{\eta_{heat}} \times Q = 1 \times \left[1.1 \times 0.87 \times (1 - 0.9) + \frac{0.2}{0.55} \right] = 0.459 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{h} \quad (8)$$

According to Equation 8, a typical μ CHP system has a very high REMM efficiency, ψ_r , which may reach 0.9.

In Equation 8, 0.55 is the partial First Law efficiency of the thermal power output of the μ CHP system. There will be a surplus CO_2 emission for HRV with $COP = 4$, when compared with the μ CHP reference system, which provides heat to the building (365 K) and waste heat (285 K) replacing HRV: $(0.46 + 0.205) \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{h} - 0.459 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{h} = +0.206 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{h}$ net emission responsibility (surplus) for HRV.

This argument shows that μ CHP systems may be preferred over HRV units in green buildings as a virtue of the Second Law analysis, which is linked to ΔCO_2 emissions. Figure 3 compares the $\sum CO_2$ of HRV and μ CHP for different COP and T_i values, both of which may be optimized by a morphing HRV.

Figure 3. Variation of CO_2 for HRV when Compared with μ CHP with COP and T_i .

Figure 3 shows that the performance of HRV in terms of whether it is responsible or mitigating emissions depend on the *COP*. For example, if T_l is 278 K, then the minimum *COP* required for mitigation threshold is 5.3. This threshold value decreases with an increase in T_l . The dotted curve corresponds to the results from the First Law only. Accordingly, the First Law shows CO₂ mitigation potential for the HRV unit, whatsoever the *COP* is. It is also unresponsive to T_l .

Despite the clear comprehensive value of the Second Law for a complete survey and rating of HRV units, all major standards related to HRV or ERV are limited to the First Law of thermodynamics. Few of them are:

- ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 84-2013 [18],
- REHVA and EUROVENT guidebooks [19],
- EU Regulation 1253/2014 [20],
- TSE Standards [21, 22],
- EU Directives [23]
- Green Building Standards [5, 24]
- TSE EN 308 [25]

Shukuya has developed a direct relationship between exergy supply by HVAC systems for human comfort and human exergy [26]. According to his state-of-the-art review, there must be an exergy balance between an air conditioning unit, outdoor air-to-air heat exchanger, and the human exergy demand. While a human body needs to release his/her heat, it needs exergy for thermal comfort. He provided the exergy balance equation and pointed out that the *COP* of the HRV changes with the outdoor ambient DB temperature and the indoor air temperature in terms of exergy balance. In this respect he states that:

‘The conceptualization of warm and cool exergies is legitimate so that what is consumed and what are the real potentials of warmth (including hotness), and coolness (including coldness) are clearly quantified.’

This concept has been carried one step further by developing exergy-meters [27] to replace calorimeters in HVAC systems and even further, by defining the exergy value of nutrition. Exergy value of a nutritional product is simply a multiplication of its calorific value times the Carnot factor, calculated by measuring its combustion temperature in the bomb calorimeter and a reference ambient temperature, like the average temperature of the Earth, to directly relate exergy demand and supply of a human body in nutrition.

METHOD

According to the example given above, a conventional HRV unit may not mitigate any $\sum\text{CO}_2$, when the exergy basis is implemented in the calculations for a certain range of *COP*. From this perspective, the mitigation potential may be improved by thinking about a morphing HRV, which adapts itself to the instantaneous operating conditions, including the fresh air requirements. For the simplest case, an axially

morphing HRV is considered, which is shown in Figure 4. It has flexible, accordion type connectors to optimize the effective length, L_i according to the varying operating conditions and the fresh air demand. The amount of thermal power, Q to be unity (unit heat) for the sake of simplicity of the analysis.

Figure 4. Axially Morphing Sensible Heat Exchanger, HRV with Variable L_i .

The objective of axial morphing and change of the heat transfer surface is to maintain a negative $\sum \text{CO}_2$ by controlling the fan power with the following constraint:

$$(P_e + P_s) < \frac{0.95}{|Q \times (1 - T_o / T_1)|} \quad \{\text{For both air preheating and cooling}\} \quad (9)$$

Exergy-Based Definitions:

1. Transfer Effectiveness

$$\varepsilon_{x\text{-sensible}} = \frac{\left| \dot{m}_2 \left(C_{p-1} \times T_1 \times \left[1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_o} \right] - C_{p-2} \times T_2 \times \left[1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_1} \right] \right) \right|}{\left| \dot{m}_{\min} \left(C_{p-1} \times T_1 \times \left[1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_o} \right] - C_{p-3} \times T_3 \times \left[1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_i} \right] \right) \right|} = \frac{\left| \dot{m}_2 \left(C_{p-2} \times T_2 \times \left[1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_1} \right] \right) \right|}{\left| \dot{m}_{\min} \left(C_{p-3} \times T_3 \times \left[1 - \frac{T_{ref}}{T_i} \right] \right) \right|} \quad \{T_{ref} = T_o\} \quad (10)$$

2. Exergy Recovery Ratio

$$RR_{ex} = \frac{\left| \varepsilon_{x-1} - \varepsilon_{x-2} \right|}{\left| \varepsilon_{x-1} - \varepsilon_{x-3} \right|} = \frac{\left| \varepsilon_{x-2} \right|}{\left| \varepsilon_{x-3} \right|} \quad \{\varepsilon_{x-1} = 0\} \quad (11)$$

Mix with Exhaust Air (Recirculation)

Figure 5 shows that part of the exhaust air at a ratio of X is mixed with the fresh outdoor air to conserve energy, either in heating or cooling. In this case, latent exergy of the exhaust air and the outdoor supply air needs to be considered. This model excludes additional fan power for mixing (P_R) if present.

Figure 5. Recirculating Air Case in Energy Recovery $0 \leq x \leq L$

Recirculating air may be mixed either at the outdoor air inlet section (marked as 1 in Figure 2), indoor air entrance section to the heat exchanger (2), or at a variable distance in the heat exchanging medium (x) in a kind of morphing heat exchanger (3), all of which should be evaluated for maximum exergy gain. In Case 3 the position (x) may be optimized.

Case 1-Recirculation at the Outdoor Air Inlet

$$T_o' = T_E \times X + T_o \times (1 - X) \quad (12)$$

$$E_{X-total} = \left\{ \left[1 - \frac{T_o'}{T_o} \right] + \Delta \varepsilon_{LH} + \left[1 - \frac{T_o'}{T_1} \right] \right\} \times Q \quad (13)$$

Case 2-Recirculation at the Indoor Air Inlet

$$T_1' = T_i \times X + T_1 \times (1 - X) \quad (14)$$

$$E_{X-total} = \left\{ \left[1 - \frac{T_1'}{T_1} \right] + \Delta \varepsilon_{LH} + \left[1 - \frac{T_o'}{T_1} \right] \right\} \times Q \quad (15)$$

Case 3-Recirculation at a Variable Position (x)

$$T_1'(x) = T_o(x) \times X + T_1(x) \times (1 - X) \quad (16)$$

$$E_{X-total}(x) = \left\{ \left[1 - \frac{T_o(x)}{T_1(x)} \right] + \Delta \varepsilon_{LH}(x) + \left[1 - \frac{T_o'}{T_1(x)} \right] \right\} \times Q \quad (17)$$

At the mixing positions of all cases, $\Delta \varepsilon_{LH}$ may be calculated from [28]. For a given design, one of the above cases should be selected for the maximum $E_{X-total}$. Case 3 enables to operate by following the instantaneous conditions. This case remains hypothetical, until morphing technology is improved. Instead, a slit system with a finite number of mixing positions may be implemented.

CASE STUDY

Based on Figure 4 (Without recirculation), let the following equations 18 and 19 apply for predicting the temperature and fan power profiles along the morphing HRV are given:

$$\frac{T_o}{T_{i1}} = \left(\frac{L_0}{L_i} \right)^{1.5} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{(P_e + P_s)_0}{(P_e + P_s)_i} = \left(\frac{L_0}{L_i} \right) \quad (19)$$

Insert Equations 18 and 19 to Equations 4, 5, and 6:

$$\sum CO_2 = 2.1 \times \left[0.95 \times \frac{(P_e + P_s)_0}{\left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]} - 1 \times \left(1 - \left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]^{1.5} \right) \right] - 1 \times \left[\frac{0.2}{0.85} + 2.1 \times \left\{ 0.87 - \left(1 - \left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]^{1.5} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (20)$$

Unit $(P_e + P_s)_0$ at L_o , is C_o .

$$\sum CO_2 = 2.1 \times \left[0.95 C_o \times \left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]^{-1} - \left(1 - \left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]^{1.5} \right) \right] - \left[\frac{0.2}{0.85} + 2.1 \times \left\{ 0.87 - \left(1 - \left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]^{1.5} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (21)$$

$$\sum CO_2 = 1.99C_o \times \left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]^{-1} - 2.06 \quad (22)$$

Equation 23 does not yield any maximum or minimum. Instead, according to Equation 22, $\sum CO_2$ decreases continuously with L_o/L_i .

$$\frac{\partial \sum CO_2}{\partial \left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]} = -1.89C_o \times \left[\frac{L_o}{L_i} \right]^{-2} = 0 \quad (23)$$

RESULTS

Figures 6 and 7 were drawn with the above sample data. Equation 22 depends on where the electricity comes from. Three cases are shown in Figure 6, namely natural gas power plant (0.2 kg CO_2 /kW-h_{en}, 0.87 kW-h_{ex}/kW-h_{en}), lignite power plant (0.4 kg CO_2 /kW-h_{en}, 0.80 kW-h_{ex}/kW-h_{en}), on-site PV farm (only ΔCO_2 : 0.27/2.1 x 1.1 = 0.141 kg CO_2 /kW-h_{en}, 0.50 kW-h_{ex}/kW-h_{en}) and on-site PVT farm (only ΔCO_2 : 0.08/2.1 x 1.1 = 0.042 kg CO_2 /kW-h_{en}, 0.50 kW-h_{ex}/kW-h_{en}).

Results show that if the electric power comes from an onsite PVT farm $\sum CO_2$ may start to be mitigated at an L_o/L_i value of approximately 1.2 (Threshold value of morphing: retraction by 20 %). For other systems and equipment this ratio is almost one (no morphing at given design conditions). The sensitivity on the type of systems and equipment that provide electric power to the HRV is higher when $(P_e + P_s)_0$ is reduced by an exergy-based control of fan speed depending on operating conditions. For example, Figure 7, which is a replica of Figure 6 with $(P_e + P_s)_0 = 0.5$, shows how the threshold point shifts to axial expansion with the change of fan powers following the thermal loads, which depend on fresh air requirement and outdoor temperature at a given instant. Therefore, it is an operational and exergy-based control requirement to also follow the energy mix of the grid power instantly. This data is, however, available by the grid power provider. Concerning a better control for minimum emission responsibility or maximum mitigation, the cross-sectional area of the morphing HRV may be changed (lateral Morphing), as a future research step.

Figure 6. Variation of $\sum CO_2$ Performance of an Axially Morphing HRV with Different Systems and

Equipment Supplying Electric Power. Unit $(P_e+P_i)_0$.

Figure 7. Variation of $\sum CO_2$ Performance of an Axially Morphing HRV with Different Systems and Equipment Supplying Electric Power. $(P_e+P_i)_0=0.5 \text{ ke}_n$.

Concerning the effect of the outdoor temperature in terms of T_0/T_i ratio on $\sum CO_2$ for a laterally morphing HRV (Figure 8), Equation 18 replaces L_0/L_i term in Equation 22, with a different power than 1.5, because of the virtue of lateral morphing (Bidirectional Morphing). A sample result with a power of 0.5 is shown in Figure 9. Without lateral morphing solar PV and PVT does not yield emission mitigation.

$$\sum CO_2 = 1.99C_o \times \left[\left(\frac{T_0}{T_i} \right)^{0.5} \right]^{-1} - 2.06 \quad (24)$$

According to Figure 9, if the outdoor temperature in the air heating mode keeps decreasing compared to the design outdoor temperature ($T_0/T_i > 1$), the mitigation potential increases.

Figure 8. Laterally and Axially (Bidirectional) Morphing HRV.

For the PVT case mitigation potential starts when the T_0/T_i ratio is 1.1. This means that for an energy mix with 100% solar PVT, HRV starts to mitigate at about -14°C (259 K) if T_i is 285 K (15°C). Depending on the energy mix like lignite, the positive contribution of HRV for mitigation obviously becomes more at the same T_0/T_i ratio. However, the operation of HRV running on lignite power becomes obsolete (emission responsibility) when T_0/T_i ratio is less than 0.95 (Warmer outdoor t_0 temperature than the design temperature).

Figure 9. Variation of ΣCO_2 with T_0 for a Fixed T_i for Various Systems and Equipment for Power Supply.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

This research paper shows that even a seemingly simple system like HRV becomes very complicated from the environmental perspective beyond the First Law of thermodynamics. For example, even the question where the electric power becomes (energy mix) becomes an important design and on-line HRV control issue, when the matter is CO_2 emission calculations. A bidirectionally morphing HRV unit seems to be analytically solvable and digitally implementable in the field for sustainable buildings. All green building metrics are based on the First Law only [5]. Theoretically, if one installs a conventional HRV unit in a so-called green building, the outcome for most of the cases may turn out to be ineffective or even adverse, if all the exergy-components of design and operation of HRV are not considered and implemented. In this respect, the Safe and Green Building Rating System developed by the Turkish Standards Institute (TSE) [29], considers exergy components indirectly for rating green buildings. This Standard has been recently extended to Exergy Star Building Metric system [24]. Algorithms to implement the exergy-based model are recently on the way [30]. Yet much more must be done in theory and application. solution to the problem of minimizing emission responsibility in terms of the changing outdoor conditions, operating mode (air preheating or cooling in summer), morphing controls, and fan speeds. Especially during pandemic periods, the use of 100% fresh air needs in green buildings and buildings of gathering require large energy consumption and HRV or ERV units seem to be indispensable solutions. Yet their design and operation must certainly be upgraded to the Second Law. Otherwise, emission responsibilities may surpass the benefits of 100% fresh air, because CO_2 content, and global warming have direct effect on pandemic risks.

In conclusion, an optimization algorithm based on the Second Law for minimum emission responsibility and maximum mitigation seems feasible as shown in this paper and the solution depends on a technically operatable bidirectional morphing HRV [31].

To close the gap between human comfort, energy, and environment one last step is to re-define today's liner, Pareto principle-based economy by arguing that exergy a climate emergency-focused economic model

is needed [32] and considering that in this respect at the face of global warming, exergy precedes energy [33]. In quote:

‘We pay for the quantity of energy, but we only use the exergy (Quality of energy)’

Peter Novak, 2004, ASHRAE TC 7.4 Meeting

Concerning net zero or nearly zero buildings, this research has also shown that buildings must be rated in terms of exergy [34].

This research has shown that a holistic approach, including the Second Law of thermodynamics and its recent extension to emission responsibility (See Equation 1) gives the ability of comparing and generating more sustainable alternatives in the quest of global decarbonization.

SYMBOLS

C_o	Total fan power, kW
CO_2	Direct emission, kg $CO_2/kW-h_{en}$
CO_{2base}	The reference emissions responsibility of the energy sector for both power and heat, 0.63 kg/ $kW-h_{en}$
COP	Coefficient of performance
C_P	Specific heat, $kW-h_{en}/(kg \cdot K)$
E	Electric power (load), or energy, kW_{en} , $kW-h_{en}$
k	Emission responsibility factor, $kg CO_2/(kW-h_{ex}/kW-h_{en})$
L	Axial effective HRV length, m
m	Mass, kg
P	Power demand of a fan (including motor efficiency), kW
PEF	Primary Energy Factor
P_{EX}	Pumping exergy, $kW-h_{ex}$
Q	Thermal energy (Heat) or thermal power, $kW-h_{en}$, kW_{en}
RR_{ex}	Exergy Recovery Ratio
T	Temperature, K or °C
X	Recirculation air ratio
x	Axial distance from the supply air side to indoors (Figure 5)

Greek Symbols

ε	Unit exergy, $kW-h_{ex}/kW-h_{en}$
ψ_R	REMM efficiency
η_I	First-law efficiency
ΔCO_2	Nearly avoidable CO_2 emission responsibility, $kg CO_2/kW-h_{en}$
ΣCO_2	Total emissions, $\Delta CO_2 + CO_2$, $kg CO_2/kW_{en}$
ΔT	Temperature difference, K

Subscripts

B	Boiler
dem	Demand
des	Destroyed (exergy)
e	Exit (Exhaust air)
en	Energy
ex	Exergy
LH	Latent het, kW
o	Outdoor
PP	Power plant
R	Recirculation (Fan)
ref	Reference

s	Supply
<u>Acronyms</u>	
CHP	Combined heat and power (Cogeneration)
μCHP	Micro CHP (With less than or equal power capacity of 50 kW)
DB	Dry bulb (Temperature)
ERV	Energy recovery ventilation
EU	European Union
FPC	Flat-plate collector
HB	Handbook
HRV	Heat recovery ventilation
HVAC	Heating, Ventilating, and Air-Conditioning
NG	Natural Gas
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change
nZEB	Nearly-Zero Energy Building
nZEXB	nearly-Zero Exergy Building
ppm	Parts per million
PV	Photovoltaic (Panel)
PVT	Photovoltaic-thermal (Panel)
REMM	Rational Exergy Management Model
SDEWES	Sustainable Development of Energy, Water, and Environment Systems
TSE	Turkish Standards Institute

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